

ISic1291

I.Sicily inscription 1291

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 273

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) Κ(αταχθονίοις)
2. Γαλάτης
3. ἔζησε ἔτη
4. ἦ ἐποίη
5. σεν υἱὸς
6. Πριμιγένης

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

To the underworld spirits of Galates, who lived for 80 years. His son, Primigenes made this.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492895

EDCS 39101660

PHI 140781

PHI 316219

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0467 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 90

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum.* Berlin. At 3.5701

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